

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities

Work Package WP2
Communication, Dissemination and Impact Evaluation

Milestone 2
ATRIUM Communication and Dissemination Report Y1 + Plan Y2

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document is an assessment of the dissemination and communication activities for the first year of the ATRIUM Project and planning of these activities for Year 2. The assessment is based upon the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (Section 7) and the activities and results for each of the communication channels (Sections 5 and 6). The Planning is focussed upon the ATRIUM Key Target Groups (Section 2) where proposed actions with a preliminary roadmap and some new, specific KPIs are outlined for each group.

The overarching objective of ATRIUM is to **empower Arts and Humanities scholars** in their use of digital methods by **facilitating access** to a wide range of **reusable workflows** and **interoperable, composable services** offered by leading research infrastructures in the Arts and Humanities domain, these being:

- DARIAH - Digital Arts and Humanities
- CLARIN ERIC - Linguistics and language studies
- ARIADNE RI AISBL- Archaeology (data management)
- OPERAS - open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Provide wider, simplified, and more efficient access to the best research infrastructures available to researchers to conduct curiosity-driven research, irrespective of location,
2. Enable breakthrough leading-edge research services to be made available to a wider user community,
3. Exploit synergies and complementarities in order to improve and harmonise RI services across the EU and Associated Countries,
4. Train a new generation of researchers to optimally exploit all the essential tools for their research,
5. Facilitate cross-disciplinary fertilisations and a wider sharing of information, knowledge and technologies across scientific fields fostered by closer interactions between researchers active in and around research infrastructures,
6. Contribute to the better management, including implementing FAIR data principles, of the continuous flow of data collected or produced by research infrastructures.

These objectives will be achieved as follows.

1. By improving the overall metadata quality of existing catalogues and repositories distributed across the participating research infrastructures. By sharing and developing common solutions for metadata quality assessment, curation and enrichment, as well as by establishing feedback loops between catalogues and data providers, the

- discoverability of resources will be improved, helping facilitate better user access across Europe.
2. ATRIUM will make the consolidated service portfolio available to a wider user community in two ways:
 - a) by improving multilingual support for tools and services, and
 - b) by specifically targeting new communities via a multi-channel, multi-stakeholder strategy to reach a wide audience across Europe and beyond, which will be based on online outreach, project events, stakeholder forums with researchers and data providers, training measures, demonstrators and the Transnational Access (TNA) grant scheme. The results of research and development conducted in transnational activities will be available under open access licences in order to reach out and impact an even larger community.
 3. Central to the success of simplified and more efficient access (1) by the wider user communities (2) will be the creation and dissemination of workflows – (potentially complex/non-linear) sequences of steps to describe how to perform a task within the research data lifecycle and demonstrators – exemplary workflows around particular topics or data types. To make complex research workflows possible, ATRIUM will aim to improve the interoperability of the consolidated service portfolio by facilitating the composability of services offered, and aligning these technical activities with the ongoing development of EOSC, most notably the EOSC Interoperability Framework.
 4. ATRIUM will contribute to knowledge sharing and capacity building among Arts and Humanities researchers by developing a coherent curriculum to be hosted on DARIAH-Campus and running a number of training measures (workshops, both in person and virtual, as well as stakeholders forums and mutual learning exercises between researchers and data providers) which will contextualise the service offerings of the participating research infrastructures within larger pedagogical narratives on digital tools and methods. ATRIUM will make training central to the provision of services and will strengthen those with TNA measures which will give users a chance to work directly with service and data providers.
 5. ATRIUM will facilitate cross-disciplinary fertilisation and knowledge sharing by consolidating effort within various Arts and Humanities communities to establish a common research assessment framework that will encompass different research outputs (including data publications, training materials, software, exhibitions, interactive visualisations, etc.) as a contribution toward maximising the quality and impact of Arts and Humanities research in Europe, also in the context of initiatives such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).
 6. ATRIUM will strengthen data management practices amongst Arts and Humanities researchers by promoting the use of standards and FAIR principles. The proposed collaboration between the research infrastructures in this project will concretely improve findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data, especially through enhanced semantic interoperability, thus fostering the permeability of data across composable services.

From the expected results, it can be seen that ATRIUM has to communicate and disseminate across a wide range of actors from the Arts and Humanities, especially as many of the disciplines are inherently interdisciplinary and involve many different technologies. Consequently, whilst Arts and Humanities researchers and scholars will benefit the most from ATRIUM, there are also many other people who also have their part to play such as the data providers and curators, the technical staff who design the metadata schemas and support interoperability of the data, run the repositories and databases and design the tools and services within the research infrastructures. Furthermore, ATRIUM wants to reach the policy makers on one hand and the general public on the other hand who are interested in topics such as archaeology and history. In order to have an effective communication and dissemination strategy, a broad selection of channels are used to ensure that all stakeholders are reached.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows:

Section 1 (Introduction) sets the stage for the document, outlining its purpose, scope, and overall structure.

Section 2 (Target Groups) identifies specific groups the project is targeting, along with strategies for engaging them.

Section 3 (Timeline) provides a chronological plan or schedule related to the project's activities.

Section 4 (Visual Identity) describes the visual elements and branding associated with the project.

Section 5 (Communication and Dissemination Channels) details how information about the project is shared with various audiences through the different channels.

Section 6 (Events) covers both past and planned events for Year 2 related to the project, including conferences, workshops, or seminars.

Finally, Section 7 (Monitoring and Evaluation) explains how the project's progress and impact is assessed using specific tools and indicators and reports the resulting figures.

2. Target Groups

2.1 ATRIUM Target Groups

The ATRIUM Stakeholders consist of the following groups:

- **Internal stakeholders**, i.e. the Research Infrastructures and their members who are part of the ATRIUM consortium;
- **Research institutions, international networks and individual researchers** at varying career levels (PhDs, postdocs/early career researchers, senior researchers) **active in the Arts and Humanities**;
- **Support staff** who provide and maintain services used by researchers, e.g. IT staff, data curators, repository managers, etc.
- **Galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAMs)** operating in these fields;
- **Educators and students** in the related subject areas;
- **Non-academic professionals working in fields related to the Arts and Humanities** such as tourism, the cultural and creative industries, etc.
- **Non-professional participants** such as amateur archaeologists, detectorists and similar interested parties;
- Relevant **politicians, policy makers and funding bodies**;
- The **media** and the **general public**.

The first two groups, consortium members and researchers can be categorised as academics whose main interest is research with the aim of publishing papers and articles through journals and papers presented at conferences. Many are engaged with social media such as X (Twitter) and Facebook and will follow feeds relevant to their areas of interest.

The GLAMS and support staff are a far more diverse group with a common interest but different requirements according to their roles. For example, IT staff are more likely to read technology-oriented publications and attend events relating to their IT expertise whilst librarians and museums both have their own networks and membership organisations which support the protocols and requirements of their specific roles.

Education provision is also a distinct field - the primary providers are universities and similar academic institutions in the first instance with the Research Infrastructures and professional membership organisations along with some private providers running courses and workshops etc. to enable practitioners to learn new skills and competences. The key to effectively reaching these stakeholders is through their membership organisations and possibly some key international conferences and journals.

Non-academic professionals work in fields related to the Arts and Humanities where the outputs of the academic research may be packaged for use by citizens. Tourism is one such

example, which can involve people who create exhibitions and technical applications (phone apps, visual and audio guides, another is private companies who provide archaeological services that are required by national law for building and infrastructure projects (and whose outputs are often reused by academics). These stakeholders may have industry associations of their own (e.g. the European Tourism Association - ETOA) or also belong to organisations such as the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) since this covers their area of interest as practitioners rather than researchers.

Non-professional participants such as amateur archaeologists, detectorists and similar interested parties may be less easy to reach but several use social media and have Facebook groups as well as their own national associations (e.g. National Council for Metal detecting in the UK, the Scandinavian Society for Prehistoric Art).

Politicians, policy makers and funding bodies need to be aware of the progress and outcomes of the project and its impact and benefits for the Arts and Humanities. More formal means of communication such as Press releases and media coverage as well as direct contacts are the most suitable forms of disseminating this information.

The media and the general public also need to be kept informed and a proactive approach with regards to the press, radio and TV works well, especially as these channels are good for reaching the general public. The website is another source of information so it is important to use language and terminology that can be understood by everyone.

The following diagram illustrates the relationships between all the stakeholders:

Researchers whose organisations are not members of the ATRIUM Research Infrastructures are categorised as 'Indirect stakeholders', i.e. beneficiaries of the project results.

2.2 Engagement and collaboration plan

In order for the dissemination and communication of ATRIUM to achieve its aims, the strategy has to be tailored to meet the needs of a range of external stakeholders whose roles and requirements will vary widely. The following plan consists of tailored strategies to engage with the different external stakeholder groups, focusing on communication, capacity building, and collaboration for the period M13-M24. Recognizing that each group operates within its unique context, the approach emphasizes inclusivity, accessibility, and adaptability to meet their diverse expectations and missions. The proposed actions include the development of training resources, tools and services, participatory events, feedback mechanisms, and innovative technologies that align with the interests of each stakeholder group. A preliminary roadmap and a list of possible KPIs are also presented.

2.2.1 Internal stakeholders

The internal stakeholders (Research Infrastructures and their members) are mostly academics and researchers. Other roles cover technical development, project management etc. within the participating organisations. These Internal stakeholders are key to supporting the dissemination and communication strategy through their own networks and contacts and by collaborating in the events organised by the project.

2.2.2 Research institutions, international networks and individual researchers at varying career levels active in the Arts and Humanities

Researchers may come from academic institutions and independent organizations. They provide the scientific foundation and innovative methodologies needed for the development of the ATRIUM outputs and may also be the end users. Engaging this group effectively will ensure that the ATRIUM becomes a precious resource for interdisciplinary research and collaboration with other stakeholders. They have their own networks and social media groups based on their specialisms.

In this context, the ATRIUM objectives are to:

- Inform the target groups about ATRIUM and encourage them to use the services and tools provided in the SSH Marketplace,
- Obtain feedback about their needs e.g. training skills survey,
- Encourage participation in the Transnational Access programme,
- Promote interdisciplinary and international collaboration.

Researchers can be reached through a wide range of channels including the website, social media, scientific publications and conferences, events and outputs such as good practice guides and success stories.

Proposed actions

- Raise the profile of ATRIUM through social media and the website, presence at events, presentations and publications,
- Organise round tables and workshops, focussing on major conferences, to engage stakeholders,
- Promote the Transnational Access programme as widely as possible,
- Organise training events and webinars to explain how to use ATRIUM outputs according to the domain of research interest (e.g. archaeology, linguistic studies, history, etc.).

Preliminary Roadmap

- Develop a programme of ATRIUM events and co-hosted events,
- Collaborate with WP8 on the Transnational Access programme to maximise the effectiveness of the dissemination to encourage organisations to apply,
- Work with WP7 to engage feedback followed by take-up of training courses.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of (external) researchers attending webinars or workshops,
- Number of researchers who accessed TNA Grants,
- Number of researchers using the ATRIUM SSH tools and datasets,
- Volume of published research utilising ATRIUM SSH tools and datasets.

2.2.3 Support staff who provide and maintain services used by researchers

This group contributes to the infrastructure used by researchers and cultural heritage organisations such as the GLAMS. Many will be involved in the development of tools and services and the maintenance of data and research archives.

Proposed Actions

- Organise technical workshops to bring together developers, professionals, researchers, and end-users to test the ATRIUM workflows and services and co-create solutions (e.g. Researcher Forums, Mutual Learning Exercises),
- Provide channels for project updates, direct communication and integration with development tools,
- Facilitate knowledge sharing,
- Foster collaboration in the development of ATRIUM services and applications.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Identify relevant networks and publications,
- Contribute articles on the opportunities offered by involvement in ATRIUM,
- Organise workshops aimed at support staff to engage them and obtain input.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of technical personnel and other professionals, e.g. curators, repository managers, etc. participating in workshops,
- Number of articles published in relevant journals/magazines.

2.2.4 Galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAMs) operating in these fields

The GLAMs are both the public-facing custodians of cultural heritage and sources of research and knowledge. Each type of institution has its own networks and membership organisations which support the protocols and requirements of their specific roles and are valuable channels for disseminating information.

Proposed actions

- Raise the profile of ATRIUM through social media and the website, presence at events, presentations and publications,
- Organise round tables and workshops, focussing on major conferences, to engage stakeholders,
- Promote the Transnational Access programme as widely as possible,
- Organise training events and webinars to explain how to use ATRIUM outputs relevant to these types of organisations.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Develop a programme of ATRIUM events and co-hosted events,
- Collaborate with WP8 on the Transnational Access programme to maximise the effectiveness of the dissemination to encourage organisations to apply,
- Work with WP7 to engage feedback followed by take-up of training courses.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of GLAMS members attending webinars or workshops,
- Number of GLAMS employees who accessed TNA Grants.
- Number of GLAMS using the ATRIUM SSH tools and datasets,

2.2.5 Educators and students in the related subject areas

Educators, represents primary providers such as universities and similar academic institutions along with research infrastructures and professional membership organisations and some private providers who run courses and workshops etc. to enable practitioners to learn new skills

and competences. Educators serve as multipliers, integrating digital heritage tools and resources into learning environments, while students represent the next generation of cultural heritage professionals, researchers, and advocates. Engaging this group effectively will raise awareness, skill levels, and stimulate innovation in the field of digital cultural heritage. The key to effectively reaching these stakeholders is through their membership organisations and possibly some key international conferences and journals as well as social media and ATRIUM events.

Proposed Actions

- Collaborate with WP7 in the development of the ATRIUM Curriculum,
- Encourage integration and use of resources into higher education courses.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Develop training materials and courses aimed at introducing the Cloud's educational potential and demonstrating how to use the ATRIUM services and workflows,
- Organise workshops or webinars for educators on using the Cloud's resources in physical or virtual learning environments (e.g. DARIAH Campus).

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of educators trained through workshops and webinars,
- Volume of educational materials developed and distributed.

2.2.6 Non-academic professionals working in fields related to the Arts and Humanities

Members from the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) sector work in fields related to cultural heritage where the outputs of the academic research may be packaged for use by the general public. Their engagement can stimulate economic growth while fostering new ways to experience and interpret cultural assets. However, their needs differ significantly from research-focused stakeholders, requiring a more practical and business-oriented approach (e.g. access to resources, copyright clearance, tools etc.).

This group may be reached via social media, the press and media and their industry associations. The objective with this sector is to demonstrate the added value of the Arts and Humanities and the role that research plays, to promote future services and to ensure the long-term sustainability of cultural heritage.

Proposed Actions

- Partner with associations and networks to engage with and to disseminate information,
- Leverage trade fairs (such as CLiC-it, international book fairs, and other design/tourism events), to reach a broader audience,

- Facilitate access to resources for creative innovation.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Identify and categorise CCIs in partner regions by sector (e.g., tourism, media, AR/VR development), and their key associations and events,
- Organise a programme in collaboration with partners to do short presentations and disseminate information at industry events,
- Create materials to highlight ATRIUM services and resources of interest to the CCIs.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Attendance at CCI-focused events,
- Number of CCIs accessing ATRIUM services and resources.

2.2.7 Non-professional participants such as amateur archaeologists, detectorists and similar interested parties.

Non-professional participants, including citizen scientists, cultural heritage enthusiasts, and the general public, may not be directly involved in the project but contribute to the arts and humanities in the wider socio-economic context. Their involvement may range from actively helping preserve and record cultural heritage, to participating as volunteers on archaeological excavations. Highlighting research activities such as ATRIUM can encourage active participation in heritage-related initiatives.

This group of stakeholders will be focussed on their particular interest across a range of channels. As well as the more traditional TV, radio and press, social media plays an important role (e.g. Facebook groups, Twitter feeds) so dissemination needs to be across a broad range of channels whilst also targeting interest groups.

Proposed Actions

- Partner with local communities to organise participative events and community engagement campaigns,
- Survey the non-professional communities identified in Task 2.3 to understand their needs and requirements,
- Leverage input from the non-professional communities identified in T2.3 to refine the ATRIUM workflows and demonstrators.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Organise community events and demonstrations to promote ATRIUM with Task 2.3.
- Develop an effective multi-channel communication campaign to raise awareness about ATRIUM,
- Develop an editorial plan of success stories involving ATRIUM outputs that are likely to engage a non-professional audience.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Attendance at community-based events and workshops,
- Number of non-professional communities involved in Task 2.3,
- Use of ATRIUM workflows and demonstrators by non-professional communities.

2.2.8 Relevant politicians, policy makers and funding bodies

Decision makers, including policymakers, funding bodies, and governmental organizations, play a visible role in shaping the landscape of the arts and humanities (e.g. by providing funding and regulatory frameworks). Their support is highly relevant for ensuring the long-term sustainability of all organisations involved including the Research Infrastructures as well as the other stakeholders. However, engaging this group effectively requires translating technical and research outcomes into actionable insights and demonstrating socio-economic impacts aligned with broader policy priorities. This is not an easy task in general. The usual channels of social media and the website, project events and more formal means of communication such as press releases and media coverage as well as direct contacts are the most suitable forms of disseminating information to this group of stakeholders.

Proposed Actions

- Create concise, visually engaging policy briefs summarising ATRIUM's objectives, progress, and societal impact (i.e. simplify the project complexity in bite sized information),
- Tailor content to align with EU-level priorities, such as the European Green Deal, digital transformation, and cultural sustainability,
- Organise roundtable discussions or panels involving policymakers and cultural heritage leaders to emphasise ATRIUM's alignment with European cultural policies.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Develop an initial policy brief outlining ATRIUM's contributions to European cultural priorities,
- Organise targeted events for policymakers.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of policy briefs and reports disseminated,
- Attendance and feedback from policymakers at ATRIUM events.

2.2.9 The media and the general public

The general public and the media may not be directly involved in the project but contribute to the arts and humanities in the wider socio-economic context. Citizens are the key audience for the GLAMS and CCI's whilst the media are an important interface between the two, the latter providing information to the public about cultural events and exhibitions, archaeological

discoveries, etc. Highlighting research activities such as ATRIUM can increase societal engagement and foster better public awareness, build trust, and encourage active participation in heritage-related initiatives.

Since citizens vary widely in their interests and educational levels, dissemination requires a broad approach. Generally, older people may rely more on the press, radio and TV for their information whilst younger audiences prefer to use social media. The channels selected by ATRIUM are the most widely used and accessible to this group as well as to a wider audience. The website is another source of information so it is important to use language and terminology that can be understood by everyone across all the channels. In addition to direct approaches to the media by researchers, journalists will often use these channels to source their information, supplemented with interviews and information sent by projects for the publication of articles in mainstream publications (digital and paper-based).

Proposed Actions

- Organise booths and have short presentations at cultural events attended by the general public, e.g. TourismA in Italy,
- Use partners to implement these initiatives at a regional level,
- Publish success stories which relate to ATRIUM tools and resources.

Preliminary Roadmap

- Develop an effective multi-channel communication campaign to raise awareness about ATRIUM,
- Identify public events and organise an ATRIUM presence at these with partners,
- Develop an editorial plan of success stories involving ATRIUM outputs that are likely to engage a non-professional audience.

Possible Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Number of participants in community events,
- Number of subscribers to the ATRIUM newsletter,
- Website and social media metrics.

2.3 Stakeholder analysis

The Stakeholder analysis summarises the information needs of each target group and the best delivery methods for engaging and involving them.

Stakeholder group	Description and examples	ATRIUM-related Interests	Importance	Channels for outreach
Research Infrastructure members	RI Managers, decisions makers and researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of the shared infrastructure - Details about innovations, new tools and methods - Best practice, guidelines and training opportunities - Conferences and other events. 	Very high - partners need to be fully engaged in order to get their full support for the project, and to spread news about ATRIUM via their own networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Internal meetings - ATRIUM conferences/ events - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.) - Newsletters (internal/ external) - Publications
Researchers	The communities of researchers, networks and institutions active in the Arts and Humanities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Details about how ATRIUM will innovate research - Access to data and resources - Recent developments in relevant RIs - Forthcoming events, workshops and training opportunities - Details about innovations and access to new tools and methods 	Very high - the ATRIUM communities need to be convinced that the project will enhance their research activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Publications - Conference presentations - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.) - Direct networking and via partners' dissemination channels
GLAMs and professionals, support staff	GLAMs active in the Arts and Humanities; non-academic professional working in fields such as data/information management or the cultural industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview about the ATRIUM mission and its progress - Relevant training and workshops - Details about innovations and access to new tools and methods - Best practice guidelines 	Medium to high - outreach beyond academia is highly desirable; GLAMs are important providers of data and expertise to RIs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Publications - Press releases - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.)
Educators and students	Educators and students at varying levels in the Arts and Humanities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview about the ATRIUM mission and its progress - Information about skills requirements (WP 7) - Details about innovations and access to new tools and methods - Best practice guidelines 	Medium to high - Humanities educators need to be aware of evolving skills requirements and contribute to the education of the next generation of researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Publications - Press releases - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.)

Citizen scientists	Specific communities identified for involvement in ATRIUM: - Swedish Rock Art Research Archives - Metal detectorists - NURNET, the Nuraghe network from Sardinia - Pelagios Network - Citizens with special needs	- Overview about the ATRIUM mission and its progress - Details about innovations and access to new tools and methods - Best practice guidelines	High: Citizen scientists make a valuable contribution to the research and involvement of non-professionals in the Arts and Humanities which leads to a better understanding and appreciation by society as a whole.	- Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Publications - Press releases - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.) - Direct networking with ATRIUM
Politicians, policy makers and funders	All the institutional or individual actors that frame the wider context of (European) humanities research/RI development	- Overview about the ATRIUM mission and its progress - Innovation potential and benefits ATRIUM offers to stakeholders and end-users - Socio-economic impact	High: their support is needed to ensure the long term future of the Arts & Humanities RIs	- Direct networking - Policy briefing - Press releases
Media/general public	Media outlets and individuals with an interest in research in the Arts & humanities	- Overview about ATRIUM mission and its progress - Benefits, including socioeconomic impact - involvement of non-professional communities	Medium to high: outreach is very important to demonstrate benefits of public investment into research.	- Press releases/media coverage - Website/social networks

2.4 Involving new communities through participatory research

The ATRIUM project aims to foster collaboration between professional researchers and non-professional communities across Europe to preserve cultural heritage through various participatory research initiatives. The emphasis on non-professional involvement helps democratise access to heritage conservation and ensures a broad spectrum of perspectives and expertise are included in the project's initiatives.

To this aim, a research strand is dedicated to the analysis of the ways of engaging a selected number of non-professional communities. The dual purpose is to foster the interest of non-professional communities in curiosity-driven activities and to gather feedback on the implementation of ATRIUM workflows, service and demonstrators. The analysis focuses on five non-professional communities involved in the ATRIUM project under Work Package 2 (WP2), Task 2.3. Each of these communities contributes to different subtasks and plays a crucial role in participatory research, preservation, and dissemination of knowledge on Europe's cultural heritage.

To gather information on the state of the art, needs, and requirements of the non-professional communities involved in ATRIUM, the project created a dedicated survey. The collected information facilitates the creation of standardised workflows that enhance data and service interoperability across Research Infrastructures, supported by demonstrators addressing real-world, research-driven questions in the arts and humanities.

The main results of the analysis of the responses to the questionnaire are outlined below along with a summary of the key findings and recommendations.

Metal detectorist communities (Subtask 2.3.1)

Community activities and challenges

UK: The community primarily comprises hobbyists, focused on identifying metal artifacts in non-restricted areas, with finds contributing significantly to national archaeological databases like the Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS). Challenges include delays in reporting and identifying finds.

Czech Republic: Metal detecting is strictly regulated, requiring collaboration with authorised institutions. A digital scheme, AMCR-PAS, formalises amateur-professional collaboration, but participation is limited due to legal and cultural barriers.

Potential contributions from ATRIUM

Metadata extraction tools: For structured documentation of finds, supporting identification and integration into databases.

Automatic image recognition: To classify artifacts efficiently, aiding both professionals and amateurs.

Geospatial visualisation tools: To enhance analysis and presentation of findings.

Educational resources: Adapting AMCR tools and raising awareness to expand amateur collaboration.

NURNET, the Nuraghe Network from Sardinia (Subtask 2.3.2)

Community activities and challenges

This network aims to highlight Sardinia's prehistoric and protohistoric heritage, relying on public participation for data collection and geoportal updates. Activities are largely informal, emphasising public engagement through social media and blogs.

Challenges include a lack of institutional collaboration and structured methodologies.

Potential contributions from ATRIUM

Interactive visualisation tools: To enhance the geoportal with dynamic and engaging content.

Collaborative tools: To facilitate structured data collection and feedback loops between institutions and enthusiasts.

Metadata extraction tools: To streamline data input for geoportal updates.

Swedish Rock Art community (Subtask 2.3.3)

Community activities and challenges

Community members participate in rock art documentation through licensed activities and online annotations. Outputs include data for deep learning models and contributions to the SHFA database.

Challenges include ensuring data accuracy and managing contributions from diverse participants.

Potential contributions from ATRIUM

IIIF annotation tools: To refine annotation workflows and improve data quality.

Automatic image recognition: To identify and classify artifacts within rock art images.

3D visualisation tools: To create immersive educational resources for rock art analysis.

Improving access for citizens with special needs (Subtask 2.3.4)

Community activities and challenges
Deaf community: Efforts focus on creating multimedia content in sign language to make cultural heritage accessible.
Blind community: Emphasis is on spatial descriptions, tactile models, and audio content.
Challenges include limited resources and tools tailored to accessibility needs. Deaf and blind people are often excluded from enjoying cultural heritage due to a lack of dedicated content.

Potential contributions from ATRIUM
Video glossaries: For commonly used archaeological terms in sign languages (starting with Italian Sign Language).
Metadata and automatic image recognition tools: To aid in creating alternative texts and enriching multimedia content.
3D visualisation tools: For tactile models and enriched audio descriptions.

Pelagios Network (Subtask 2.3.5)

Community activities and challenges
Pelagios supports Linked Open Data (LOD) methods for cultural heritage studies, emphasising semantic annotations and data sharing.
Challenges include aligning tools and methods with diverse partner needs and fostering widespread adoption.

Potential contributions from ATRIUM
Ontology-driven tools: To integrate structured workflows and enhance LOD capabilities.
Geotagging and collaborative mapping tools: For linking place names and historical datasets.

Visualisation tools: To explore linked data and facilitate educational outreach.

Summary of key findings and recommendations

ATRIUM's efforts in enhancing accessibility, technological integration, and community collaboration signify a holistic approach to cultural heritage management. The initiatives undertaken do not merely focus on preservation but also on education, accessibility, and participation, thereby expanding the traditional scope of heritage projects. By leveraging local knowledge, advanced technologies, and inclusive practices, ATRIUM ensures that cultural heritage is not only preserved but also actively shared and experienced by diverse audiences. The project highlights that non-professionals are more than just contributors, they are stewards of heritage, whose engagement is vital for fostering a deeper connection to the past and ensuring the sustainability of cultural heritage for future generations.

Key findings

Community diversity: The projects highlight the participation of a range of non-professional groups, from hobbyists to accessibility advocates.

Data collection: Significant volumes of new data, including photographs, annotations, and multimedia, are being generated.

Legislative considerations: Different countries enforce varying levels of legal oversight, impacting collaboration and participation.

Technology needs:

- Tools for automatic recognition, tagging, and visualisation.
- Platforms for accessible cultural dissemination.

Recommendations

Engagement strategies:

- Focus on user-friendly tools that simplify collaboration between professionals and non-professionals.
- Tailor services to the needs of specific communities (e.g., LIS videos for the deaf, 3D models for visually impaired).

Technology implementation:

- Prioritise interactive visualisation, metadata extraction, and geospatial data tools to align with community expectations.
- Pilot image recognition tools for artifact classification and annotation.

Awareness and education:

- Expand outreach via social media, workshops, and educational content to engage non-professionals.
- Collaborate with legislative bodies to standardise guidelines and encourage ethical practices.

Next steps

The results of this analysis are currently under review and will be sent to WP4 and WP5 in early 2025. As soon as the first workflow prototypes and demonstrators are available, the non-professional communities will be contacted again to test the developed results and provide their feedback on usability and usefulness.

Milestones	Deadline
Ex-ante evaluation report reviewed	Mid-January 2025
Report sent to WP4 and WP5	End of January 2025
First prototypes ready to be tested (workflows, demonstrators)	End of June 2025
Preliminary feedback on the developed prototypes	End of December 2025

3. Timeline

Regular updates after every major milestone in the project, such as the delivery of significant deliverables, conference attendance, presentation and news items will be disseminated via social media, news items on the ATRIUM website, blog posts, etc. These items will also be featured in the quarterly newsletters, as a round-up of all major milestones, project updates, and news and event items. The quarterly ATRIUM newsletter will serve as a centralised repository of the latest news and events associated with the project. The first newsletter will be scheduled for the second week of June 2024, and after that, at 3 month intervals throughout the duration of the project.

Project Milestone	Date
ATRIUM Launch event	1/2/24
Social Channels activated	12/2/24
Project logo and visual identity defined	12/03/24
Communications kit available	15/03/24
Transnational Access Scheme Call Opened	20/3/24
Website launch	28/03/24
First Newsletter published	12/6/24
Activate ATRIUM Youtube channel	July 24
ATRIUM informational video launch	August 24
First Researcher Forum in Poznan	17/10/24
Ex-ante report of the non professional communities involvement	End of October
First Mutual Learning Exercise	Spring 2025
Second Researcher Forum	Summer 2025
Second Mutual Learning Exercise	Fall 2025
Ex-ante impact evaluation analysis	12/2025
ATRIUM mid-term event	12/2025
First materials and videos to demonstrate the use of the ATRIUM	As soon as the results

workflows and demonstrators	are available
ATRIUM Skill Set assessment and Gap Analysis report	M20-M24

4. Visual Identity

A specific logo has been created by commissioning a professional graphic designer who worked with us extensively to create a “brand” for ATRIUM consistent with the project’s objectives, goals, and values.

ATRIUM full logo with custom typography

The colours selected for the visual identity of ATRIUM are consistent with the thematic focus developed with the graphic designer as we worked on the visual identity through a series of consultation sessions. The colour scheme was developed with several themes in mind, including archaeological, connectivity, bridging old and new, and coalescing of the four leading research infrastructures.

Colour palette for ATRIUM.

Textures, photos, website headers with thematic focus.

Typography chosen to reflect the project's direction.

Brandmarks were developed in a series of consultation sessions with our graphic designer. The various different colour schemes can be downloaded in the Communications Kit section of the ATRIUM website.

The ATRIUM "Brandmark" in different colours according to colour scheme

The Visual Identity of the ATRIUM project will be consistently applied across all communication channels, both online and offline, such as the project website, social media, printed communication materials, and promotional products. As such, a dedicated "Communications Kit" section of the website ensures that the visual identity of the project is accessible and downloadable, and is available at <https://atrium-research.eu/communications-kit/>

Every printed piece of material will acknowledge the EU support and relay the following text, as specified in the grant agreement. The website footer also displays the text:

"Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement n. 101132163. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

5. Communication and Dissemination Channels

5.1 Project Website

ATRIUM website homepage design.

The domain atrium-research.eu was purchased in early 2024 and is live, with relevant content segmented into Menu sections. The website has been designed to serve as the first port of call for those seeking information on the project as well as a repository of relevant information for stakeholders such as project partners and collaborators. Under the “RESOURCES” section of the menu tab, throughout 2024 the submenu tabs have been updated to categorise the information for “Transnational Access”, “Communications Kit”, “Deliverables”, “Services & Software Catalogue”, and “Workflows Catalogue”. Moving forward into 2025, provisions will also be made for the site to host the stakeholder forum ATRIUM Bridge, along with dedicated sections for the ATRIUM Curriculum and Peer Review Framework.

The goal of ATRIUM (Advancing frontTier Research In the arts and hUManities) is to bridge leading research infrastructures in arts and humanities ([DARIAH](#)), archaeology ([ARIADNE](#)), languages ([CLARIN](#)), and open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities ([OPERAS](#)).

The Arts and Humanities is a very diverse field, covering a range of disciplines and communities of practice that have different epistemological and methodological foundations: an archaeologist and an art historian studying a Mycenaean fresco will have distinct goals and approaches to describing their objects of research. A literary scholar and a linguist will come to a textual corpus with radically different senses of what a corpus is and what questions can be asked of it. Yet research infrastructures in the Arts and Humanities domain must cater to a very wide range of stakeholders and offer services that cut across discipline-specific boundaries.

ATRIUM website homepage with informational video.

Transnational Access – Travel Grants

ATRIUM will offer researchers and research teams the chance to visit 16 research infrastructures and organisations in the Arts and Humanities abroad.

[More info](#)

Transnational Access (TNA) Scheme section on the ATRIUM homepage.

Transnational Access Scheme Grants

The Second Call for TNA Applications is now open! ATRIUM invites researchers to apply for fully-funded training visits across Europe.
Closing date: 31st December 2024.

The ATRIUM project is now accepting applications for its Transnational Access (TNA) scheme, offering fully funded placements across Europe for researchers. This initiative is designed to support Arts and Humanities researchers by providing access to expert knowledge, mentorship, and tools from leading Data Management organisations

Successful applicants will have the opportunity to visit one of 14 different host organisations across Europe, benefiting from direct contact, knowledge sharing and network building. In total 388 weeks of Transnational Access visits will be provided during the ATRIUM project, aiming to support approximately 200 researchers.

There are two types of TNA applications:

- **Individual Access** – Tailored placements based on your own specific research topic that matches the specialisms of a chosen host organisation.
- **Summer School Access** – Fixed group training sessions on predetermined specialised topics that occur at several fixed points during the year.

[More about Individual Access](#)

[More about Summer Schools](#)

Dedicated TNA page on the ATRIUM site available at atrium-research.eu/travel-grants

There is a detailed section of the website under the “RESOURCES” tab on the menu which directs users to the “Services and Software” produced in association with the project. This new element is supported by a social media campaign with the accompanying hashtag #ATRIUMCatalogueSpotlight, a weekly post across all ATRIUM social media accounts which promotes a different resource on the ATRIUM Catalogue each week.

Service & Software Catalogue

The ATRIUM project promotes a comprehensive set of services & tools designed to support all the stages in the digitally enabled data-driven research in the Arts and Humanities. This curated catalogue features state-of-the-art resources for creating, processing, analyzing, preserving, and reusing digital data across various disciplines, from archaeology to linguistics.

Explore the services and tools - whether you're managing textual corpora, analyzing geospatial data, transcribing spoken field notes, or engaging in other research activities.

Discover the ATRIUM Catalogue on SSH Open Marketplace

Our list of tools and services is hosted on the SSH Open Marketplace, a comprehensive discovery portal that collects and contextualizes resources for Arts and Humanities research communities. By clicking on the titles of the tools and services, you will be taken directly to their entries on the SSH Open Marketplace where you can further explore detailed information, training materials, datasets, publications, and workflows associated with each tool. The platform not only helps you find what you need but also connects you with related publications and case studies, providing valuable context and experimenting practical applications to improve your research.

You can also explore the full list of tools and services of the ATRIUM catalogue on the SSH Open Marketplace, by simply entering the keyword "ATRIUM catalogue" into the search box on the homepage. This search will direct you to the complete list of tools and services, as well as workflows created using them.

Services & Software Catalogue

Discover the ATRIUM Catalogue on the
SSH Open Marketplace

atrium-research.eu/services

SSH Open Marketplace
Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace

DARIAH-EU

ARIADNE
Research Infrastructure AISBL

CLARIN
Common Language Resources and
Technology Infrastructures

OPERAS
open scholarly communications in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

Funded by
the European Union

Poster promoting the ATRIUM Catalogue.

Under “RESOURCES” there is also a tab for “Workflows Catalogue”, which is dedicated to collating all the workflows produced as part of the project.

Workflows

Workflows are often overlooked in the arts and humanities but are essential for research. Workflows describe specific research scenarios to provide researchers with a clear step-by-step guide to help them integrate different tools and methods to achieve their goals.

ATRIUM develops and shares workflows that help researchers integrate digital methods into their work. These guides outline how to navigate the research data lifecycle from start to finish.

ATRIUM workflows are hosted and built using templates from the [SSH Open Marketplace](#). Browse the ATRIUM Workflow catalogue below:

3 workflows

[ATR \(4\) - Layout Analysis](#) >

[Automatic Text Recognition Roadmap](#) >

[LLM-Powered Mapping of Keywords of a Research Article to Linked Data](#) >

Workflows

In the “NEWS” section of the website, there is also a “TNA BLOG” section, which features updates from the recipients of the Transnational Access Scheme (TNA) travel grants, and featuring updates from how this scheme has benefitted and supported their research in line with the goals and objectives of the project in Y1. This section is maintained and will be regularly updated with posts by recipients of the TNA Travel Grants, and used to promote the experience of the scheme both during the rolling application periods and throughout Y2.

TNA Blog

ATRIUM Training at Archaeology Data Service, University of York

by Peter Chege Gathoni

Peter Chege Gathoni from Nairobi, Kenya and [the British Institute in Eastern Africa, reports on his week at the Archaeological Data Service at University of York.

Heritage Building Information Modeling at The Cyprus Institute

by Vasos Socratous

By joining the ATRIUM Project Transnational Access Scheme (TNA), I was able to actively participate in relevant research activities ongoing at the Cyprus Institute, an experience that turned out to be enlightening and transformative. During my TNA at the VELab, I had the opportunity to understand better the specialized field of Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM).

Upscaling Research Skills Through ATRIUM Summer Schools: My Experience at the Czech Academy of Sciences in Brno

by Juan Carlos Ocampo

The ATRIUM Training School in Computational Archaeology is one of the highlights of my summer. When I found out about ATRIUM's Transnational Access Scheme grant, I knew I couldn't let this opportunity slip. But the real hook was the Summer School at the Czech Academy of Sciences in Brno: spatial data analysis, integrated archaeological data, and reproducible coding skills in R.

TNA Blog section on ATRIUM Website.

5.2 Social Media

After establishing dedicated project pages on both LinkedIn and Twitter/X, ATRIUM is expanding its online community across social media through LinkedIn (649 connections at the time of writing) and Twitter/X (371 followers at the time of writing) with a systematic social media campaign, inviting connections to follow the page and engage with the content as it is posted regularly. Social media icons and a pinned Twitter feed feature on the project website to incite website visitors to connect with the profiles. Other contacts will be acquired through the registration process on the ATRIUM website, which is currently underway. There is also a dedicated ATRIUM YouTube channel which will be used to publish informational videos about ATRIUM that are produced over the duration of the project. An ATRIUM Bluesky account has also been established as of December 2024, with projected plans for expanding followers and engagement on the platform in place for 2025 (see Figures below).

ATRIUM Research
@ATRIUM_EU

ATRIUM is an @EU Commission funded project Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities, bridging @DARIAHEU, @ARIADNE_RI, @OPERASEU & @CLARINERIC 🇪🇺

📍 Europe 🌐 atrium-research.eu 📅 Joined February 2024

97 Following 122 Followers

Posts Replies Highlights Articles Media Likes

Pinned

ATRIUM Research @ATRIUM_EU · Apr 4

ATRIUM invites researchers to apply for fully funded Transnational Access (TNA) training visits to support their research 🏛️

ATRIUM bridges @DARIAHeu, @CLARINERIC, @ARIADNE_RI & @OPERASEU to advance frontier knowledge in the arts & humanities.

➔ Visit: atrium-research.eu/travel-grants/

ATRIUM Twitter/X profile.

ATRIUM Bluesky profile as of December 2024.

ATRIUM LinkedIn page

A dedicated ATRIUM YouTube channel.

5.3 Newsletters and press releases

A quarterly ATRIUM newsletter will be distributed to the ATRIUM mailing lists, with designated sections for “Project news”, “Conference Participation”, and updates from participants of the

Transnational Access Scheme (TNA) such as interviews, profiles, and accounts of their placements, whether through individual access or summer school participation. The first newsletter was scheduled for 12th June 2024, with the Autumn newsletter sent on 25th October 2024, and the Winter newsletter by the end of December 2024. Visitors to the ATRIUM website are invited to sign up to a mailing list to receive these updates, with details how on how to sign up at the footer of the ATRIUM website homepage and also available at this link which can be shared as a URL: <https://atrium-research.eu/ninja-forms/1kqsp/>. Previous versions of all newsletters will be archived on the ATRIUM website, at the designated "Newsletters" tab of the "NEWS" item on the main menu: <https://atrium-research.eu/newsletters/>. Three newsletters have been sent in Y1, and for Y2, four are planned to correspond with each quarter.

The first ATRIUM newsletter which was sent in June 2024

Subscribe to our mailing list and newsletter

Email Address *

First Name *

Last Name *

Institution

Submit

Subscription option on the homepage of the ATRIUM website

Other Research Infrastructures that have connections with media outlets will be engaged throughout the process. Popular online platforms that have relevance to the project will be engaged via social media to promote project news and events.

A [press release template](#) is available in the Shared Drive, and this template will be used for media announcements, individual emails to prospective stakeholders, and when official communications need to be disseminated through mailing list.

info@atrium-research.eu
atrium-research.eu

PRESS RELEASE

ATRIUM (Advancing Frontier Research In the Arts and Humanities) is a European Commission-funded research project, launched in January 2024, which will run for four years. The project bridges four leading European Research Infrastructures: **DARIAH** (arts and humanities), **ARIADNE** (archaeology), **CLARIN** (languages), and **OPERAS** (open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities), and brings 17 partners and 12 affiliated entities from 12 countries across Europe.

ATRIUM offers a series of fully-funded research placements at leading data management organisations across Europe through its **Transnational Access (TNA) Scheme**. Both summer school and individual placements are available. Find out more at atrium-research.eu/travel-grants

Visit atrium-research.eu for more information.

5.4 Communication materials

At the time of writing, the first informational flyer has been produced which is available on the ATRIUM website, a generic flyer to share information about ATRIUM and direct interested parties to the Transnational Access (TNA) Scheme call. The flyer will be translated in all the partners' languages. As the project progresses and based upon context, equivalent flyers, posters and other printed promotional materials will be produced.

ATRIUM

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities is a European Commission-funded project facilitating access to digital research infrastructures across disciplines, languages and media. It bridges four leading Research Infrastructures: DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN, and OPERAS.

Objective 1: Enhancing Access by improving metadata quality in catalogues & repositories.

Objective 2: Making Research Widely Available to diverse communities by emphasising citizen science and inclusivity, as well as providing grants for training visits.

Objective 3: Developing Research Workflows and Demonstrators to be shared and hosted on the SSH Open Marketplace.

Objective 4: Provide training by developing the ATRIUM curriculum and running training sessions (ATRIUM Bridge) based on identified user needs.

Objective 5: Establishing the Peer Review Framework to incentivize varied research outputs necessary for building and maintaining innovative research infrastructures.

Objective 6: Strengthening Data Management Practices by promoting FAIR principles – making data more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

ATRIUM in Numbers:

29 PARTNERS	14 COUNTRIES	4 YEARS
4 RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES	200 ARTS & HUMANITIES RESEARCHERS SUPPORTED THROUGH TNA	10 MILLION EURO BUDGET

ATRIUM's **Transnational Access (TNA) scheme** offers researchers the possibility to apply for a fully funded placement at 16 Digital Humanities & Data Management organisations across Europe. With over €450,000 budget, the TNA travel grants will support around 200 Arts and Humanities researchers to gain access to expert knowledge and advice.

Find out more about the Transnational Access Grant Scheme.

SCAN FOR TNA INFO

DARIAH-EU
Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities

ARIADNE
Research Infrastructure AS2L

CLARIN

OPERAS

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement n. 101132163. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Info@atrium-research.eu | atrium-research.eu | @ATRIUM_EU | ATRIUM: Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts & Humanities

ATRIUM Informational Flyer with QR codes directing to the website.

The flyer has been translated into all the partners' languages (i.e. Czech, Dutch, French, German, Greek, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Serb, Swedish) to facilitate distribution at local events, with PDF versions available on the ATRIUM website [here](#)

A standard presentation has also been prepared, in a downloadable template form to ensure maximum compatibility with ATRIUM branding and visual identity, that is freely available on the website: <https://atrium-research.eu/communications-kit/>

5.5 Publications

Scientific and non-scientific publications will contribute to the dissemination process, increasing visibility, ensuring quality and credibility and providing open access.

All publications will be kept in a repository on a dedicated section of ATRIUM's website, under the menu heading "Publications".

Potential and prospective journals to publish ATRIUM-related content in:

- *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal*: <https://transformations.episciences.org/>
- KULA journal: <https://kula.uvic.ca/index.php/kula>
- *International Journal of Architectural Heritage* (Taylor & Francis): <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/uarc20/current>
- *Journal of Cultural Heritage* (Elsevier): <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-cultural-heritage>
- *Language Resources and Evaluation*: <https://link.springer.com/journal/10579>
- *Natural Language Processing*, Cambridge University Press: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/natural-language-engineering#>
- *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*: <https://aclanthology.org/venues/tacl/>
- *Post-Medieval Archaeology*: <https://spma.org.uk/our-journal>
- *Computational Humanities Research*, Cambridge University Press: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/computational-humanities-research/information/about-this-journal>

5.6 Videos

The first informational video introducing ATRIUM as a project has been uploaded to the dedicated ATRIUM Youtube channel and is embedded on the website homepage. This 4 minute video features interviews with representatives from each Research Infrastructure, who outline the project's goals and introduce the project, explain briefly how it relates to the four research infrastructures and ask each interviewee to mention an important aspect of ATRIUM, such as bridging the four infrastructures, facilitating access to workflows, establishing demonstrators, developing training resources, and the TNA scheme. Four shorter videos dedicated to explaining what the project means for each of the four Research Infrastructures were also produced in addition to the informational video, and have been distributed via the project's social media accounts.

A second video will be produced before M24, featuring work completed under the auspices of ATRIUM, with special focus on researchers who have completed the TNA scheme.

6. Events

The project's participation in various conferences, events, and gatherings is referenced on the website, which has a designated section for events, as well as qualifiers:

- ❖ "Upcoming"
- ❖ "Past"
- ❖ "Organised"
- ❖ "Presented at"
- ❖ "Supported"
- ❖ "Endorsed"

Events

- All events
- Upcoming
- Past
- Organised
- Presented at
- Supported
- Endorsed

Society for American Archaeology Annual Meeting

Date: 18 April, 2024
Location: New Orleans, USA

The International Congress on Archaeological Sciences in the Eastern Mediterranean and the Middle East (ICAS-EMME)

Date: May 15-18 2024
Location: Cyprus

SSH Open Marketplace ATRIUM Workshop

Date: June 18, 2024
Location: Lisbon, Portugal

EAA (European Archaeological Association) Conference

Date: August 28-31 2024
Location: Rome, Italy

OPERAS Conference 2024

Date: 24-26 April 2024
Location: Zadar, Croatia

DARIAH Annual Event 2024

Date: June 18-21 2024
Location: Lisbon, Portugal

Events page on ATRIUM website

Workshops & webinars: In addition to the presence at conferences, ATRIUM will provide a series of online workshops and webinars on the project's core topics and demonstrators on an online platform such as Zoom. Video recordings of these events will be available on a dedicated project video channel and integrated with proper contextual information and metadata into DARIAH-Campus.

Researcher Forum and Mutual learning exercise: In the context of Task 7.2 The ATRIUM Bridge, ATRIUM will organise a series of workshops for researchers and data providers. The Researcher Forum is a workshop with researchers using a service aiming at addressing the RIs' needs to

better understand their users' roles, needs, build more beneficial contacts, develop and innovate around services. The Mutual Learning Exercise is a workshop for a service that uses data provided by others and it can be used to build relationships with data providers, address challenges, and develop new features.

Step-by-step promotion of events through ATRIUM outreach channels, such as scheduled social media posts, resharing and reposting of tagged posts on project social media, updates in the newsletter, etc. At a later project stage, the ATRIUM integrated services and use cases of digital research workflows will be demonstrated, including at some conferences, such as a tutorial or workshop, along with dedicated Hackathons.

Event promotion, coverage and follow-up will be central for ATRIUM's outreach. Every ATRIUM related event, workshop, or webinar will be communicated and posted on the dedicated section of ATRIUM's website and social media channels, covering activities before, during and after an event. For example, a news item from each event where the project has been represented, such as ATRIUM's recent presence at the OPERAS conference which saw a news item, <https://atrium-research.eu/training-interopability-and-multilingualism-atrium-at-the-opera-s-conference/>, and [promotion across social media](#).

Y1 ATRIUM Participation in Events

2024 Event	Date	ATRIUM Participation	Event Listing on ATRIUM website
Conference SAA Annual meeting in New Orleans	18th April	Speaker	https://atrium-research.eu/events/society-for-american-archaeology-annual-meeting/
ATRIUM Services and Semantics at the OPERAS Conference, Zadar	24th April	Speaker	https://atrium-research.eu/events/opera-s-conference-2024/
The International Congress on Archaeological Sciences in the Eastern Mediterranean and the Middle East (ICAS-EMME)	15th May	Speaker	https://atrium-research.eu/events/the-international-congress-on-archaeological-sciences-in-the-eastern-mediterranean-and-the-middle-east-icas-emme/
Historic England HQ,	11th June	Organiser	

London			
SSH Open Marketplace ATRIUM Workshop at DARIAH Annual Event, Lisbon	18th June	Organiser	https://atrium-research.eu/events/dariah-annual-event-2024/
ARIADNE RI Training School - Heraklion	18th July	Speaker	
EAA Conference, Rome	29th August	Organiser, Chair, Speaker	https://atrium-research.eu/events/eaa-european-archaeological-association-conference/
atRium Training School in Brno	16th September	Organiser	https://atrium-research.eu/events/atrium-training-school-in-brno/
ATRIUM Researcher Forum in Poznan	17th October	Organiser	https://atrium-research.eu/events/atrium-researcher-forum/
ATRIUM workflows and demonstrators at DaSCHCon: Archaeology & Interoperability, Switzerland	23rd October	Speaker	https://atrium-research.eu/events/daschcon-archaeology-and-interoperability/
Digital Archeology CAA-SE	21st November	Speaker / General project communication	

Key events, Calls for Papers, and upcoming deadlines shall be monitored and updated on the shared ATRIUM Events Google Calendar, which all partners have been invited to subscribe to, and can be accessed here:

<https://calendar.google.com/calendar/u/0?cid=MWY3MTQzZGZhNDVmMGI2OGJmN2FmODg1ZmY1ZDI4NDMyOWMwMjgyNzk3OTBiNWE1N2YwYTcwY2lyZmMzYjUxNEBncm91cC5jYWxlbmRhci5nb29nbGUuY29t>

An internal spreadsheet is in use to keep track of upcoming and relevant events (see below for the events planned in Y2).

Events planned in M13-M24

Date	Location	Event Title	Website
21-23 February 2025	Florence, Italy	tourisma – Salone Archeologia e Turismo Culturale	https://www.tourisma.it/home/
3-7 March 2025	Bielefeld, Germany	DHd-Jahreskonferenz	https://dhd2025.dig-hum.de/
5-7 March 2025	Tartu, Estonia	DH Nordic and Baltic 2025	https://dhnbeu.com/conferences/dhnb2025/
14 & 21 March 2025	Online	Joint event ATRIUM-Skills4EOSC on the Fair-by-design methodology	
28 March & 4 April 2025	Online	TNA One-Year Showcase	
Spring 2025	TBC	Baltic DH Forum	
5-9 May 2025	Athens, Greece	CAA Annual Conference	https://caa-international.org/conference/future-conferences/caa2025/
13 May 2025	Online	FitSM training	
4-6 June 2025	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Digital Humanities Benelux 2025	https://2025.dhbenelux.org/
17-20 June 2025	Göttingen, Germany	DARIAH Annual Event	https://annualevent.dariah.eu/
15-18 July 2025	Lisbon, Portugal	DH2025, Alliance of Digital Humanities Organisations	https://dh2025.adho.org/
4-15 August 2025	Prague, Czechia	Summer School on the 'Data Literacy with R for Students of Humanities'	https://atrium-research.eu/digital-research-infrastructure-for-language-technologies-arts-and-humanities-charles-university-prague-czechia-summer-school/
1-5 September 2025	Berlin, Germany	ATRIUM Summer School on Automatic Text	

		Recognition	
3-6 September 2025	Belgrade, Serbia	Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)	https://www.e-a-a.org/ea2025
8-10 September 2025	Florence, Italy	IEEE International Conference on Cyber Humanities (IEEE CH)	https://www.ieee-ch.org/
8-13 September 2025	Siena, Italy	Digital Heritage - International Congress 2025	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
TBC	TBC	LREC – The International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation	http://www.lrec-conf.org/
30 September – 2 October 2025	Vienna, Austria	CLARIN Annual Conference	https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-annual-conference

7. Monitoring and Evaluation

7.1 Monitoring tools

Supervision of the communication and dissemination activities is carried out regularly. In order to best monitor the impact of the communication and dissemination strategies, a [shared form](#) has been created for partners to log and record their activities. The form is composed of several sections which represent different means and tools to spread information about the project and the results: Web Pages (pages or posts on websites/portals), Social Pages (posts on social channels), Newsletters / Press releases, Publications (scientific and non scientific), Dissemination Materials, Events (presentations at third party events or events organised by the partner), Other activities (press releases, TV/radio campaigns, videos, etc.). The form also allows for the reporting of relevant news for publication on the project website. Through this instrument it is possible to monitor the evolution of each type of activity and the specific target audience reached. All the partners are reminded periodically to update their activities.

The project website plays a fundamental role in the communication and dissemination activity and it is of paramount importance to monitor access and activities (e.g. accesses, downloads, etc.). For this purpose, an analytics tool has been integrated into the website from the beginning.

Regular WP2 team meetings are planned on a monthly basis to review activities, assess progress, and plan for the upcoming months. In addition, as part of the general monitoring of the progress of all the project activities, a monthly summary report is produced for each Work Package. This report includes information on: actions/outcomes achieved within the WP, collaboration with other WPs and input needed, recent decisions, next actions / steps, problems encountered / solutions recommended.

7.2 Impact Evaluation

In the impact evaluation work, first an ex-ante evaluation investigates the current situation regarding digital services available from ATRIUM partners for humanities researchers and other users (e.g., cultural heritage institutions, citizen science communities) and the potential future use of the services which ATRIUM will integrate and demonstrate based on workflows for processing different types of data (WP4 and WP5).

In the first project year, a study has been investigating the connection between the humanities and citizen science. This work is related to the involvement in ATRIUM of non-professional communities (T2.3) and focuses on challenges and requirements for successful humanities citizen projects. The study will be completed in April 2025.

The ex-ante evaluation can also benefit from studies that are being carried out in other WPs, especially a survey in WP7 on the skills required for the active use of the ATRIUM services (T7.1). This study asked the providers of the services to list the skills needed and then surveyed the humanities research community to find out whether these skills are there or not.

The results of this survey are expected for August 2025. In WP7, the results will inform the development of training materials for the ATRIUM Curriculum (T7.3). For the ex-ante evaluation the survey results will provide a basis for evaluating the potential future use of the ATRIUM services and workflows which are being developed in WP4. The results of this evaluation are expected for September 2025.

The interim impact evaluation report, due in December 2025 as part of D2.1, will summarize the results of the mentioned studies as well as describe the achieved, workflow-based integration of ATRIUM services and use of operative services by humanities researchers and other users (i.e., some first impact stories).

The final impact evaluation, due in M48 as part of D2.2, will analyse the impact of the project in terms of the improvement it brings to different aspects of humanities research, for example, through the improved use of digital archives, digital workflows and services integrated in the ATRIUM infrastructure.

The primary impact target group of ATRIUM are humanities researchers, already advanced or starters in digital research practices, who will use the integrated RI services for leading-edge and cross-disciplinary projects. However, the impact regarding other target groups will be analysed as well, including cultural heritage institutions and citizen science communities. For example, this concerns the take-up of ATRIUM services and know-how by cultural heritage curators to increase the “FAIRness” of their digital collections/archives (e.g., richer metadata and semantics), and make them available for research and other purposes. Such usage will also be fostered by an active stakeholder forum of providers and users of ATRIUM services, datasets and workflows.

7.3 Key Performance Indicators

7.3.1 Communication and Dissemination indicators

To evaluate the success of the dissemination activity it is possible to enumerate a series of indicators.

Quantity Indicator (cumulative)	M6 (actual)	M12 (actual)	M24 (planned)	M36 (planned)	M48 (planned)
Avg. number of website visitors per month	90	97	150	200	250
Total number of website visitors	361	781	2,000	3,500	5,000
Number of EU/EEA countries reached through website	4	32	40	45	50
Number of contacts in the mailing list	67	128	200	250	300
Number of X/Twitter followers	260	371	500	800	1000
Number of X/Tweet impressions		200	400	600	900
Number of LinkedIn followers	298	649	600	800	1000
Number of Bluesky followers	-	15	300	500	800
Number of press releases	1	2	3	4	6
Number of YouTube subscribers	-	41	100	150	200
Number of cumulative YouTube views	-	339	500	1000	2000
Number of leaflets/other publicity materials distributed	200	300	600	900	1,300
Number of presentations at third party events	2	6	12	24	40
Number of attendees reached at conferences	100	300	300	600	1,500
No. of articles in scientific or professional journals	-	1	4	7	10
Number of views of deliverables on website / Zenodo	30	40	80	130	200

Summary of website traffic from June-December 2024

The indicators are mainly positive with most targets reached and exceeded. The total number of website visitors is slightly lower than the targets, but growing steadily month on month. However, the social media numbers for X (Twitter) and LinkedIn are well over target which compensates for this.

7.3.2 Impact indicators

In the Grant Agreement, a number of impact indicators has been defined. These come on top of the indicators for the dissemination and communication activities which will drive the awareness, take-up and use of the ATRIUM technical services and other services (e.g., the ATRIUM Curriculum) and products (e.g., the ATRIUM Peer Review Framework).

The set of expected impact results (quantified indicators) within the project duration include:

- Already active users of ATRIUM integrated services: 400
- Platform for defining, using and sharing A&H digital research workflows: 25 workflows defined and most already used in ATRIUM demonstrators and by other users
- Linkable FAIR cultural heritage datasets: 40 already used in demonstrators showing enhanced flow of data from repositories to and between research services
- ATRIUM Curriculum (training program) for starters in advanced digital A&H research: 300 trained
- ATRIUM Peer Review Framework (e.g., for review of shared research workflows) adopted by A&H research centres: 40 centres
- Cross-disciplinary projects fostered: 5 projects, involving scholars in different A&H disciplines and possibly others
- Participation of external citizen science communities in the project: 6

A more detailed description of these indicators and related quantifiable project results is presented in the Grant Agreement, Part B, section 2.1: Project's pathways towards impact.

Consortium

Research Infrastructures

Beneficiaries

Affiliated Entities

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